

PREPARATION AND ELECTROMAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBES BUCKYPAPER/EPOXY RESIN NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

A new technique involving buckypaper (prepared by millipore filtration of MWCNTs suspension) /resin infiltration to prepare multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) reinforced nanocomposites has been developed.

MWCNTs with different aspect ratio are investigated to fabricate buckypaper. The result shows that the MWCNTs with an aspect ratio of 200 were easily to form buckypaper. The electromagnetic parameters of buckypaper composite and traditional composite are tested comparatively. Since the uniformity of the MWCNTs in buckypaper, the dielectric properties were greatly increased, and the buckypaper composite was demonstrated to be a potential absorbing material.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted great attention in the past decade due to their interesting properties^[1-2]. Particularly, their extraordinary electrical properties make CNTs have potential application as filler in microwave absorbing materials^[3-5]. However, fabricating CNTs-reinforced composites with uniform dispersion is a great challenge, since CNTs have a strong tendency to form agglomerates in matrix^[6-8]. A new technique involving buckypaper/resin infiltration to prepare multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) reinforced nanocomposites has been developed. The MWCNTs buckypaper^[9-11] prepared by millipore filtration of MWCNTs suspension is an entangled mat of MWCNTs, which is a highly porous mesh structure. With the same concentration, nanocomposites prepared by buckypaper possess better dispersion than the composites manufactured by the traditional mixing processing. Therefore, it will show higher electromagnetic properties.

2 Experiment

2.1 preparation of buckypaper

Buckypapers are thin membranes or films formed with well controlled and dispersed porous network of MWCNTs. MWCNTs with different aspect ratio were purchased from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co.Ltd, and the purity was claimed to be 97% by the manufacturer. All of the buckypapers are prepared utilize a typical process^[12]: A specific amount of MWCNTs was grinding with a little water using a mortar and pestle. A selected surfactant (X-100) and 1000 ml deionized water were added into the paste and conducted 1hour sonicating to form a stable suspension. The final concentration of the suspension was 10–60 mg /L. The suspension was filtrated through a filter with the aid of vacuum to fabricate the buckypaper. Following filtration, the buckypaper were thoroughly washed with deionised water to remove the dispersion surfactant. The buckypapers were carefully peeled off from the filter after drying in a vacuum oven.

2.2 Fabrication of composites

The buckypaper nanocomposite was prepared by resin infiltration. Epoxy resin used for this research was E-51 and the curing agent was tetraethylene pentamine (TEPA) were mixed at a weight ratio of 100:12. After infiltration, the buckypaper with mixture of resin and curing agent were cured at 70 °C for 1h and 120 °C for 2h.

The conventional nanocomposite prepared by directly mixing MWCNTs into resin was also fabricated for comparison with buckypaper nanocomposites. The composite are cured at the same condition.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology of MWCNTs was observed by FETEM (Tecnai G2 F20). The microstructures of treated MWNTs are observed with FESEM (Apollo-300 OXFORD Corporation). The complex relative permeability and relative permittivity of buckypaper composites and conventional composites in the frequency range of 8.2~12.4GHz are tested by 8722ES vector network analyzer for the further calculation and analysis of their absorbing properties.

3 Result and discussion

3.1 Technological parameters of millipore filtration

The buckypapers prepared with different aspect ratio are observed with FESEM as shown in Figure 3.1. In Fig. 3.1, it was the micrograph of the surface of buckypaper made by MWCNTs with different aspect ratio, which was 2000 for Fig. 3.1a, 1000 for Fig. 3.1b and 200 for Fig. 3.1c, respectively. The differences of aspect ratio were clearly shown in the HRTEM images of MWCNTs in the top right corner of the SEM images. As it is shown in Figure. 3.1a, there are obvious cavities on the surface of buckypaper made by MWCNTs with a high aspect ratio of 2000. Moreover, it was so fragile that it hardly can be peeled off from the millipore filter. However, with the reducing of aspect ratio, the surface of buckypaper turns to be smoother. When the aspect ratio was as low as 200, there was scarcely any pores on the surface and the surface was uniform and dense. This result might be due to the MWCNTs with high aspect ratio was easier to be entangled into agglomerates, even with the existence of the surfactant.

Therefore, MWCNTs with low aspect ratio are selected to make buckypaper in this work. The buckypaper made by optimized nanotubes are shown in Figure. 2. It shown that the film was very integrity and the nanotubes are distributed uniformly in the film.

3.2 The electromagnetic properties of composites

MWCNTs buckypaper composites are prepared based on optimized nanotubes. The electromagnetic parameters of both the MWCNTs composite and MWCNTs buckypaper composite are analyzed comparatively. For both of the composites, the complex permeability is negligibly small as compared with complex permittivity, indicating that the dielectric loss mainly contributes to the reflection loss of composites. As a result, the data of the complex permeability was not displayed in this article. Fig. 3.3 manifests the complex permittivity of

traditional MWCNTs composites and buckypaper composite, which represents the typical dielectric properties of the samples investigated in this work. CNTs have high conductivity which tends to form conducting network in the composite based on its special morphology^[13] which leads to the increase of the dielectrical properties in composites. In Fig 3.3, compare with the MWCNTs composite, the dielectrical properties of buckypaper composite was greatly enlarged, especially the imaginary part of permittivity, which implied the buckypaper composite possessed better microwave absorbing property. The result could easily explained by the micrograph of the buckypaper. From the SEM image of buckypaper, it can be seen that the MWCNTs have a uniformed distribution, which could be maintained when fabricating the composite^[14]. The conducting network was perfect in buckypaper composite, and the electron could run smoothly through the conductive path of buckypaper composites. On the other hand, in the traditional composite, the MWCNTs were inclined to agglomerate in the resin as reported by other articles. Therefore, the conductivity network was not complete for the concentration of fillers in some places and the deficiency in other places.

3.3 The microwave absorbing properties of composites

For further investigation of the microwave absorption, the reflection loss of traditional MWCNTs composite (2wt %) and buckypaper composite (2wt %) are calculated, and the reflection loss curves are shown in Fig. 3.4.

The reflection loss of a microwave absorbing layer is given by^[15]

$$R(dB) = 20 \log \left| \frac{Z_{in} - 1}{Z_{in} + 1} \right| \dots\dots (3.3)$$

$$Z_{in} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_r}{\epsilon_r}} \tanh \left[j \left(\frac{2\pi}{c} \right) \sqrt{\mu_r \epsilon_r} f d \right] \dots\dots (3.4)$$

where Z_{in} is the normalized input impedance, c is the velocity of electromagnetic waves in free space, f is the microwave frequency, and d is the thickness of the absorbing layer. Therefore, microwave propagation in electromagnetic media is largely determined by the complex relative permeability and permittivity of the absorbing materials. All the calculated values were predicted based on a constant thickness $d = 2.0$ mm.

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For the traditional MWNT composite, the reflectivity in the range of 8~12Hz was a little lower than 0, which means the absorbing was not intense. However, for the buckypaper composite, the reflectivity was as low as -9 dB, and the frequency width of the $R < -4\text{dB}$ was 3Hz. Therefore, preparing the nanocomposite through the buckypaper was an excellent process to obtain microwave absorbing material.

To investigate the possible mechanisms and effects giving rise to the enhancement of microwave absorptions, the absorbing theory should be introduced [16]. When a bunch of electromagnetic waves enter a medium, part of the waves is entering into the medium, and the other is reflected by the surface of the medium. The filler with high dielectric properties could absorb the wave entering into the composite and turn the electromagnetic energy into other forms of energy such as heat. This mostly relies on the electric loss and magnetic loss of the fillers. Consequently, the result of electromagnetic parameters could explain the result of absorbing properties of composites. For buckypaper composite, the imaginary part of permittivity was greatly enlarged compared with the traditional composite, which means that the microwave could greatly be absorbed by the fillers and transform into other energy in buckypaper composite. In conclusion, the uniformed distribution of MWCNTs in buckypaper give rise to the perfect conductivity network in the composite which lead to the intense dielectric loss of buckypaper composite and make the buckypaper composite an excellent microwave absorbing material.

4. Conclusion

MWNT buckypaper composite is prepared successfully with optimized MWCNTs with an aspect ratio of 200. The dielectric property of buckypaper composite was extraordinarily higher than the traditional composite due to the uniformed distribution of MWCNTs in the buckypaper. The enlarged dielectric properties especially the dielectric loss makes the buckypaper composite a potential material in microwave absorbing area.

Fig.3.1. Micrograph of the surface of buckypapers

Fig.3.2. The buckypaper made by optimized nanotubes

Fig.3.3 The permittivity of composites

Fig.3.4 The reflection loss of composites

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